

SOME REMARKS ON THE HISTORIOLOGY OF THE REIGN OF AMIR TIMUR

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10071419>

ANNOTATION: The article examines sources on the history of Amir Temur and the Timurid era. Reviews of the great commander will be discussed in the sources provided. The names of primary and secondary sources are given.

KEY WORDS: Amir Timur, Timurids, source, year, birth, study.

One of the most important positive changes in the history of independence during the years of independence was the acquittal of the national hero of our people, Amir Temur, whose name was unjustly denounced during the dictatorial Soviet rule. At the initiative of the First President of the Republic I.Karimov, his 660th anniversary was widely celebrated in 1996 at the international level, recognizing his great services to the development of the nation and the state. Attitudes toward the individual have risen to the level of public policy. During the years of independence, a lot of important work has been done on the personality of Amir Temur, his state, domestic and foreign policy, the rule of the Timurids. In particular, 1996 was declared the Year of Amir Temur, the Amir Temur International Fund was established, the State Museum of the History of the Timurids was opened, the Amir Temur Order was established, and in April 1996 it was initiated by UNESCO[1]. An international scientific conference was held in Paris, many historical sources on the period of Amir Temur and the Timurids were translated, and so on. Undoubtedly, historians have also made a worthy contribution to the determination of historical truth. A.Urinbaev, B.Akhmedov, D.Yusupova, U.Uvatov, A.Muhammadjanov, A.Ahmedov, O.Buriyev[2] and many other scientists translated historical sources, carried out noteworthy researches: Many researchers, such as Ziya, H. Boboyev, S. Khidirov, Sh. Uljayeva, D. Obidjanova, H. Fayziyev, B. Usmanov, O. Rakhmatullayeva[3], in their research managed to reveal historical and legal aspects.

The history of Amir Temur and the Timurids is being studied with great interest not only in our republic, but also by the world scientific community. K. Marlow wrote a historical play about Amir Temur in 1588, the famous German composer G. Handel wrote an opera in 1724, and the American writer E. Poe wrote a poetic poem in 1827. The research works of R.Grosse, L.Keren, Y.Rose, H.Hukham, F.Mans, G.Glombek, A.Deraga, K.Yenoki, E.Manau, M.Rossati[4] and others have gained great fame in the historiography of the XX century.

It should be noted that by 2000, the number of works about Amir Temur and the Timurids in the languages of European peoples was 500. In 2006, on the eve of the internationally celebrated 670th anniversary of Amir Temur, the famous French scientist L. Keren conducted a study in French in Paris entitled "Journey to Samarkand, the time of Amir Temur[5]"

In conclusion, it can be said that many historians and politicians in many countries are interested in the great ruler who has his place in world history, and many sources have been created to this day.

References:

1. 630-сон 29.12.1994. Amir Temur tavalludining 660 yilligini nishonlash to'g'risida (lex.uz)
2. Ibn Arabshoh. Ajoib al-maqdur. – B.68

3. Brion Marsel. Menkim, Sohibqiron-Jahongir Temur. (Marsel Brion FransiY. Tarjimonlar: F.Ro‘ziyev, F.Tilovatov). – T.: Yangi asr avlodi, 2014. – 572 b.;
4. Keren L. Amir Temur saltanati// fransuz tilidan tarj. va izohlar muallifi B.Ermatov; maxsus muharrir

